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New Data Types

D1: Linking Surveys and Digital Trace Data

An introduction and guide for researchers

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Executive Summary

An increasing number of researchers in the social sciences use digital trace data to answer a variety of research questions. While these data have certain advantages over survey data, such as being less influenced by social desirability, they also have their own limitations, including a lack of information about individuals or relevant outcome variables. Linking surveys and digital trace data is an approach that allows for combining the unique strengths of these two data types and addressing their respective limitations. This guide provides an introduction to this approach that holds great potential for research in the social sciences. After providing a definition of digital trace data and briefly presenting their key strengths as well as notable limitations, different ways of accessing digital trace data are discussed as they determine how these data can be linked with survey data. Following this, different ways of linking surveys and digital trace data are introduced and compared. The guide then also addresses ethical considerations for working with linked survey and digital trace data as well as things that need to be considered for sharing and archiving these data. While finding the best solutions for linking surveys and digital trace data always depends on the specific kinds of data and the research interest, this document is meant to provide some general guidance for researchers who want to combine these two data types.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

ADP	Slovenian Social Science Data Archives
AOIR	Association of Internet Researchers
API	Application Programming Interface
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GESIS	GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
ICPSR	Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research
SERISS	Synergies for Europe’s Research Infrastructures in the Social Sciences
SOMAR	Social Media Archive
TARKI	TARKI Data Archive
ToS	Terms of Service
UK	United Kingdom
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

Introduction & Background

While survey data is still the most commonly used type of data in quantitative social science research, in recent years, researchers have increasingly begun to incorporate digital trace data into their work. Digital trace data have been defined as “records of activity (trace data) undertaken through an online information system” (Howison, Wiggins, & Crowston, 2011, p. 769) and they “can be collected from a multitude of technical systems, such as websites, social media platforms, smartphone apps, or sensors” (Stier et al., 2020, p. 504). Besides their source, another relevant distinction for digital trace data is whether these traces are intentional or unintentional (Hox, 2017). Examples of intentional digital traces include Tweets, posts on Facebook or Reddit, or comments in the discussion section for a news article. Unintentional traces, on the other hand, are data collected about the users of specific platforms, services, or devices that are not actively and consciously produced by those users. An example would be usage or location data collected by apps on a smartphone. Menchen-Trevino (2013) makes a similar distinction between participation traces and transactional data.

The uses of digital trace data in research are as diverse as their sources and types. They can and have been used to study a large variety of topics ranging from political communication to health behaviour, personality, or the formation and expression of attitudes about various subjects. The young field of computational social science that “leverages the capacity to collect and analyse data with an unprecedented breadth and depth and scale” (Lazer et al., 2009, p. 722) strongly relies on digital trace data to answer a wide range of research questions.

Compared to self-report data from surveys, the major advantages of using digital trace data¹ are that they are nonreactive, substantially less prone to being affected by social desirability, and not affected by recall bias. On the other hand, digital trace data also have their own set of limitations. Most importantly, digital trace data often lack important individual-level information about the characteristics of the people whose data are being used. While there are tools for inferring user attributes from digital trace data (see, e.g., Sloan et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2019), these inferences can be wrong (or biased), so self-report data is typically the better choice for gathering detailed individual-level information about the users. This is similar for attitudes and beliefs. While some of those can be inferred, for example, from data like posts on social media, self-reports require respondents to state their attitude or belief in clear and explicit terms. In addition, inferring certain user attributes may also be limited or restricted by privacy laws or terms of service of specific platforms. Besides user characteristics, many (behavioural) outcome variables that are of interest for social science research, such as voting behaviour, are typically missing from digital trace data. Combining

¹ Other terms used to describe this type of data include non-designed, organic or found data, although these are typically understood/defined more broadly (to, e.g., also include transactional data, such as payments, or other records of activity).

self-report data from surveys and digital trace data can help to overcome some of the respective limitations of the two data types (Stier et al., 2020). After discussing different options for collecting digital trace data in the following section, this guide will cover the topics of different ways of linking, ethical considerations for working with linked survey and digital trace data, and things to consider for sharing and archiving these data.

Collecting and working with digital trace data

With their everyday use of technology, people produce enormous amounts of digital trace data. Notably, however, much of these data are not (easily) accessible for academic researchers as they are controlled by private companies that own or produce the platforms, services, and devices whose use generates the data. This causes a situation in which “social scientists have access to more data than they ever had before to study human society, but a far smaller proportion than at any time in history” (King & Persily, 2019, p. 3). Despite these restrictions, there are different means with which researchers can collect digital trace data. Breuer, Bishop, and Kinder-Kurlanda (2020) distinguish three options. Researchers can 1) collect the data themselves, for example, via Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) or web scraping, 2) cooperate with companies that produce or hold the data to gain privileged access (e.g., as embedded researchers), or 3) purchase the data (e.g., from data resellers or market research companies). All three options have their own advantages and disadvantages as they differ with regard to several key aspects, including the required resources (costs, skills, and time), control over the collection process, quantity and quality of the data, and researcher independence. Researchers need to take these factors into account when choosing a method for collecting digital trace data. First and foremost, however, their choice of the appropriate collection method(s) should be guided by their research interests to ensure that they collect the data that they need to answer their research question(s).

Up until now, the most popular method for collecting digital trace data has been the use of APIs. However, APIs typically have limits with regard to the amount and type of data that can be accessed, and these limits can change drastically as they depend on decisions made by the companies that offer the APIs. In the wake of the Cambridge Analytica scandal (Isaak & Hanna, 2018), *Facebook* essentially cut off access to user data via its APIs for researchers, and many other companies also reduced or limited API access. For that reason, some scholars have argued that academic research using digital trace data is facing an “APIcalypse” (Bruns, 2019) or argue that it is entering a “Post-API age” (Freelon, 2018). These developments make alternative ways of collecting/accessing digital trace data even more important for academic researchers. Some researchers have argued for an increasing importance of web scraping (Freelon, 2018; Mancosu & Vegetti, 2020), which is an alternative to using APIs for researchers who want to (and can) collect the data themselves. Others have proposed new models of partnerships between academic researchers and private (tech) companies as a way forward (King & Persily, 2019; Puschmann, 2019). Regarding the option of purchasing digital trace data, there are many companies that

provide social media analytics services. While their services are targeted at commercial companies (mostly to assess and increase audience reach, e.g., for advertising purposes), these services can also be of interest to academic researchers. Besides the question of pricing, such data may, however, only be of limited use for academic researchers as they are often not collected on the level of individual users. For individual-level data, several market research companies now offer tracking panels consisting of internet, smartphone, or social media users who agreed to have (parts of) their online activities tracked. For an internal research project at GESIS, data from such a commercial panel was used and linked with other types of data.

Case Study Example

For an internal research project at GESIS, researchers purchased data for one year from a tracking panel maintained by a German market research company. The panellists agreed to use software that integrates with the web browsers on their desktop computers and/or mobile devices (smartphones or tablets) to track their browsing activities. A subset of the panellists also agreed to have the use of apps on their mobile phones tracked. The web and mobile app tracking data are provided by the market research company. The researchers invited participants of this tracking panel to participate in a series of online surveys to collect data about their sociodemographic characteristics, attitudes, and opinions. As part of these surveys, respondents were asked whether they would be willing to share some of their data from Twitter, Facebook, and Spotify with the researchers. To collect Twitter data for the participants, the research team asked respondents for consent and their Twitter handle, and used the Twitter APIs to follow their activities on the platform. For the Facebook data, participants were asked to install a browser plugin that collects the public posts from their Facebook feeds plus some metadata about those (see Haim & Nienierza, 2019). Spotify data was collected via an online app created by an external academic collaboration partner that connected to the platform's API. Purchasing the tracking data and using this as a starting point for further data linking had several advantages. It was the most effective way (in terms of required resources) to access individual-level web tracking data for a small project with limited funds. In addition, participants of this panel could be assumed to have a higher willingness to agree to the sharing of the additional social media data. Inviting respondents to do so in the online surveys also ensured that explicit informed consent could be obtained. Disadvantages of the digital trace data collection methods employed in this project include opt-in bias and limitations with regard to data sharing as the collected data are sensitive in several regards, and the contractual agreement with the market research company also includes restrictions to this regard.

In addition to the three options described in detail by Breuer et al. (2020), there are two other options for researchers who want to use digital trace data that represent further alternatives to using APIs: Researchers can a) partner with users to collect data or b) use existing collections of digital trace data.

In his "proposal for ethical distributed research", Halavais (2019) proposes "partnering with users to collect big data" (p. 8) as an option for avoiding limitations imposed on researchers by platform terms of service (ToS). Breuer et al. (2020) also call this the "data donation"

approach. Many services that collect digital trace data (including major social media platforms) allow their users to export their personal data. In the data donation approach, users are asked to share these data with researchers (for a good example of an implementation of this approach, see Thorson et al., 2019). An alternative to the data export option is the use of browser plugins or similar tools provided by researchers that users install and use to capture some of their digital trace data (for an example, see Haim & Nienierza, 2019). The key advantages of these approaches are that they are more transparent for the users, actively involve them, and facilitate getting informed consent (we will discuss the issue of informed consent in more detail in the following sections). The main disadvantage is the effort required from participants.

Apart from collaborating with the users, another option for accessing digital trace data is to use existing data collections. There are, for example, several curated collections of Twitter data available that can be (re-)used for research, such as *TweetsKB*², *Documenting the Now*³, or the *GESIS Social Media Monitoring*⁴ for the German federal election.⁵ Using existing collections has the advantage that researchers do not need to concern themselves with the actual collection of the data (and the various practical and ethical challenges this can entail). However, the main limitation of this approach is that researchers have to take the data as they are. While some large collections (like *TweetsKB*) allow the creation of filtered subsets of data, it is not possible for researchers to extend these collections. While some of the collections are being updated, the key limitation is that researchers who want to (re-)use data from them have no direct control over the collection process.

Summing up the different types of options for accessing digital trace data, researchers can:

1. Collect digital trace media data
 - a. Themselves (via APIs or web scraping)
 - b. By partnering with users (e.g., via data donation)
2. Enter direct partnerships with platforms/service providers to access digital trace data
3. Use existing data
 - a. Purchased from companies (e.g., data resellers or market research companies)
 - b. From existing collections of digital trace data (created by or for academic researchers)

² Tweets KB, <https://data.gesis.org/tweetskb/> (date of access: 23/11/2020)

³ Documenting the Now data catalogue, <https://catalog.docnow.io/> (date of access: 23/11/2020)

⁴ GESIS Social Media Monitoring, <http://mediamonitoring.gesis.org/> (date of access: 23/11/2020)

⁵ The SERISS "Report on legal and ethical framework and strategies related to access, use, re-use, dissemination and preservation of social media data" (Hagen et al., 2019) also lists a few other existing resources in Chapter 4.3 on the "Sharing of social media data".

What is important to note and be aware of, regardless of the specific method of acquiring the data, is that for most digital trace data, researchers not only have to take into account the interests of the people whose data they collect/use (especially with regard to their privacy) but also those of the commercial companies that own and operate the services whose use generates the data (as typically laid out in the ToS; see Van Atteveldt et al., 2019; 2020). This has major implications for the sharing and archiving of these data (as discussed later in the section on sharing and archiving linked survey and digital trace data).

Ways of linking surveys and digital trace data

As noted in the introductory section, linking surveys and digital trace data is a viable approach for combining their unique strengths and addressing some of their respective limitations. On an abstract level, there are two types of data linking: Data linking can either be a process of combining data from multiple sources into one dataset or of establishing links between different datasets by finding or assigning common identifiers. The former is much more common in the social sciences and, hence, also the focus of this guide. As this is the typical approach in substantive social science research with digital trace data, the focus of this document is also on what is called deterministic linkage (in contrast to probabilistic record linkage), meaning that there are unique identifiers (or a combination of identifiers) that allow researchers to create an unambiguous link between units of observation (such as individual users) across multiple datasets (Sayers et al., 2016). However, also within this category of data linkage, there are different ways in which the survey and digital trace data can be linked. Importantly, the way in which the digital trace data are collected (see previous section) largely determines how they can be linked with survey data. In essence, the ways of linking surveys and digital trace data differ across two key dimensions: a) The dimension or level (unit of analysis) on which they are linked, and b) the point in time in the research data life cycle at which they are linked. Regarding the level of the linking, survey and digital trace data can either be linked on the individual or the aggregate level (e.g., aggregated for specific geographic regions and/or time periods). This is related to the categorization of horizontal and vertical trace data made by Menchen-Trevino (2013). The former are broad collections of digital traces without much information about individual observations (i.e., typically a large number of observations but only a few variables). An example of this type of data would be a collection of all Tweets for a set of hashtags. Vertical digital trace data, on the other hand, contain detailed information about a limited set of individuals (i.e., few observations and many variables). Combinations of surveys and digital trace data typically fall somewhere in the middle of the continuum between these two types. Another distinction is that surveys can be collected for the same units of observation at the same time (ex-ante linking) or collected independently and combined at a later point in time (ex-post linking). In the case of ex-ante linking on the individual level, which, arguably, produces the kind of data that most social scientists are predominantly interested

in⁶, researchers can either start with/from the survey or the digital trace data. That is, they can either first collect digital trace data (e.g., via an API) and then invite the users whose data they collected/acquired to participate in a survey (given, of course, that they can identify and contact the users), or they can first conduct a survey and therein ask respondents whether they would be willing to the sharing or tracking of (some of) their digital trace data. Notably, both ways are associated with specific sampling biases (Jürgens et al., 2019; Sen et al., 2019).

Types and ways of linking surveys and digital trace data

How are the survey data and digital trace data collected?

- For the same units of observation at the same time: Ex-ante-linking
- Collected independently and combined at a later point in time: Ex-post linking

On what level do the survey data and the digital trace data exist?

- Individual level: Individual-level linking
- Aggregate level: Aggregate-level linking

In the case of individual-level ex-ante linking: What is collected first?

- Start with the survey and ask for consent to collect and link digital trace data as part of the survey
- Start with the digital trace data (e.g., via API), and then contact users to invite them to a survey

What the different types of linking should illustrate is that the ways in which the (digital trace) data are collected or accessed determine the way in which they can be linked with survey data. Of course, as always, which type of linking researchers choose should be determined by their research interest. However, they also need to take into account what data are available to them. While linking surveys and digital trace data, undoubtedly, holds great potential for research in the social sciences, this linked data also comes with its own set of challenges. Besides potential biases introduced by the sampling, data collection, and processing methods, researchers (as well as archivists) working with linked survey and digital trace data also have to take particular ethical issues into consideration.

⁶ Of course, aggregates of digital trace data linked to survey data can be interesting for social scientists as well. For example, aggregates of digital trace data for specific times or regions can be linked to survey data based on variables, such as country/area of residence or time since or when a specific digital platform or service has been used. A benefit of such aggregated data is that they are already anonymized which can facilitate data sharing.

Ethical considerations for working with linked survey and digital trace data

When working with linked survey and digital trace data, it is important to be aware of and follow applicable legislation regulating the use of both survey and digital trace data. While a detailed discussion of legal aspects relevant for working with linked survey and digital trace data is beyond the scope of this guide⁷, two legal domains are important to consider: privacy & data protection law (for both types of data) and copyright (especially for certain types of digital trace data). Regarding privacy and data protection, for the EU, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)⁸ is the most relevant piece of legislation as it regulates how personal data can be used (including for research). Notably, GDPR only regulates the use of personal data and, hence, is not relevant if only fully anonymized aggregated data are used. For the case of linking survey and digital trace data, this relates to ex-post linking of aggregated survey and digital trace data in which units of observations are not individuals but, e.g., countries, regions or time periods. Where personal data are used, there needs to be a legal basis for collecting and processing the data. In social science research, a commonly used legal basis is informed consent from the people whose data are being used. While from the legal perspective this may not always be strictly necessary as there are other possible legal bases for processing and storing personal data, such as “legitimate interest” (Mancosu & Vegetti, 2020), from an ethical perspective, obtaining informed consent from individuals is generally the best practice when linking survey and digital trace data on the individual level (Menchen-Trevino, 2018). For the case of linked survey and digital trace data, the best way to obtain informed consent is through the survey. Importantly, respondents need to consent to the collection and the linking of their data and should be informed about what data are collected, what they are used for, and how they are stored, and how/by whom they can be accessed. The latter point should also differentiate between the time during the study (researchers/research group) and after the study when the data are archived and, ideally, published for secondary use. Informed consent needs to adhere to legal regulations (GDPR in Europe) and satisfy ethical standards (as defined, e.g., by Institutional Review Boards). A practical challenge in this is to appropriately inform respondents without overwhelming and confusing them with too many (technical) details. For a set of studies in the UK with linked survey and Twitter data, Sloan et al. (2020) have developed a very helpful template for an informed consent procedure that can be adapted for other studies working with combinations of surveys and digital trace data.⁹

⁷ Section 4.2 of the SERISS “Report on legal and ethical framework and strategies related to access, use, re-use, dissemination and preservation of social media data” (Hagen et al., 2019) provides a good overview of the legal issues related to the use of social media data.

⁸ Complete guide to GDPR compliance, <https://gdpr.eu/> (date of access: 23/11/2020)

⁹ The SERISS report on the “Workshop on use of social media data in social surveys” (Straume et al., 2018) also provides some helpful guidance for formulating an informed consent for studies using and linking social media data.

Key questions for informed consent developed by Sloan et al. (2020)

What information will you collect from my Twitter account?

What will the information be used for?

Who will be able to access the information?

What will you do to keep my information safe?

As digital trace data are often highly disclosive, it is good practice to keep the survey and digital trace data separate and only combine what is necessary for specific analyses. This requires the establishment of principled processes for splitting and combining the data. One such workflow is presented by Sloan et al. (2020) for a combination of survey and Twitter data. In essence, this proposed workflow ensures that there is no combined dataset that contains the full survey and digital trace data. Again, while the specific example is the combination of survey and Twitter data, the workflow by Sloan et al. (2020) can also be adapted for other types of digital trace data. In addition to this systematic processing, Sloan et al. (2020) propose three other principles for maintaining/increasing data security: Data reduction, controlled access, and data deletion. Regarding data deletion, the authors note that “data should only be held for as long as is necessary for analysis to be conducted” (p. 72). Of course, researchers may also want or have to archive the data (see following section). In that case, the other two principles – data reduction and controlled access – become even more relevant. For many analyses, it is not necessary to use the full raw data. Hence, it may be a good privacy-preserving option to use with (and/or later on share and archive) aggregated data. Importantly, while the disclosive nature of some types of digital trace data is very obvious, such as the real names or photos in social media profiles or posts, the disclosure risk of other digital trace data may be less straightforward to identify. For example, location data collected via smartphones or other devices may show patterns that indicate where a person lives or works. Another example is web tracking data. If web tracking data contain full URLs, they may contain identifying tokens, such as e-mail addresses or user names. Also, if people have personal (or professional/business) websites that they frequently visit, they can be identified through their web tracking data. For these reasons, reducing or aggregating the data (e.g., by only including visits to locations or websites visited by a certain share of people in the above examples) can be a viable way for increasing data privacy while at the same time not reducing the analysis potentials of the data too much.

The above examples relate to specific types of digital trace data. While suggestions and solutions developed for one kind of digital trace data may be adapted for other kinds, there is always the trade-off between the specificity and generalizability of recommendations and guidelines. In addition to specific examples, as described by Sloan et al. (2020), there are also general ethical guidelines for research involving digital trace data. One of the most comprehensive sets of such guidelines comes from the Association of Internet Researchers

(AOIR; franzke et al., 2020). Another helpful resource is the *SERISS* “Report on legal and ethical framework and strategies related to access, use, re-use, dissemination and preservation of social media data” (Hagen et al., 2019). What is important to keep in mind is that there are no universal solutions when it comes to research ethics for linked survey and digital trace data. What ethical issues need to be addressed and how they should be addressed always depends on the specific data at hand as well as national legislation and institutional policies. One area where this becomes particularly apparent is the sharing and archiving of these data.

Sharing and archiving linked survey and digital trace data

As discussed in the previous section, many of the ethical questions related to working with linked survey and digital trace data become especially obvious and relevant when it comes to sharing and archiving such data. Of course, generally, the FAIR principles should also be applied to linked survey and digital trace data, meaning that they should be findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. In addition to the need to preserve the privacy of participants, researchers also need to take into account the interests and requirements formulated by commercial companies whose platforms and services provide or produce the data (as usually laid out in their ToS). While the interests of these companies and academic researchers often overlap with regard to protecting the users’ privacy, they can be in conflict regarding the sharing and archiving of the data (Breuer et al. 2020). While researchers typically want to make the data available for other researchers to make their research transparent and reproducible, private companies may have business interests that conflict with these open science principles. To what degree academic research is or can be bound by ToS of platforms or services that hold or produce digital trace data is an ongoing legal debate in many countries. Similarly, researchers and archives have different positions on this. Until now, both researchers and archives have aimed for complying with ToS as much as possible, but future legislation (or court decisions) may change this (Mancosu & Vegetti, 2020). Another consideration is that finding solutions for ToS-compliant sharing and archiving of digital trace data is a moving target as ToS can and do change (often also in the time between the data collection and the intended sharing/archiving, and sometimes even during the data collection). Also, due to the specific characteristics of digital trace data, some of the data management practices of researchers are different from those commonly used for survey data. This, of course, also affects linked survey and digital trace data and has implications for archives that want to preserve such data (Hemphill et al., 2020). Given these challenges regarding the sharing and archiving of digital trace data that researchers and archivists have to deal with, it is not surprising that the number of archived digital trace datasets in general, is still relatively low (see the section on social media data in the CESSDA Training Data Management Expert Guide¹⁰). However, as the experience with these data is

¹⁰ CESSDA Training Data Management Expert Guide, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3820473> (date of access: 23/11/2020)

increasing among researchers and archivists, the number of archived datasets containing digital trace data continues to grow. A few of the European social science data archives already hold several such datasets (see, e.g., Kinder-Kurlanda et al., 2017 for an example from GESIS). Overall, archives have been increasing their efforts in archiving digital trace data. A very prominent example is the development of the Social Media Archive (SOMAR) at ICPSR (Hemphill et al., 2018).

As this is a fairly new methodological approach, the number of studies in the social sciences that have linked survey and digital trace data are limited (Stier et al., 2020). Hence, it is clear why only very few studies of this type have so far been archived. For this reason, there also are no specific guidelines for the sharing and archiving of linked survey and digital trace data. However, there are some guidelines for the ethical sharing of social media data (Bishop & Gray, 2017; Mannheimer & Hull, 2018; Weller & Kinder-Kurlanda, 2016; Williams et al., 2017) that can also offer guidance for the archiving of combined survey and digital trace data. Two other useful resources in this context are the “Appendix A: Short guide on legal and ethical issues for the researcher to consider when using social media for research” in the aforementioned *SERISS* report (Hagen et al., 2019) and the CESSDA webinar on “Archiving Social Media Data”¹¹. Again, there are no universal solutions, and the sharing and archiving of linked survey and digital trace data require case-by-case decisions and consultation. However, as both digital trace data and their combination with surveys are becoming increasingly popular in the social sciences, solutions for sharing and archiving these data are continuously being developed and refined.

Conclusion & Outlook

Linking surveys and digital trace data holds great potential for social-scientific research by allowing researchers to combine the unique strengths of these two data types. As there are many different types and ways of accessing digital trace data, there are also various options for linking them with survey data. For that reason, the specific practical and ethical challenges that researchers need to address when working with linked survey and digital trace data always strongly depend on the particular types of data that are used. Nevertheless, as this guide has hopefully illustrated, there are some general recommendations and existing work on digital trace data that can provide some guidance for researchers interested in working with linked survey and digital trace data. While most researchers from the quantitative social sciences are quite familiar with survey data and the practical and ethical considerations it requires, digital trace data are a new format for most researchers as well as archivists. Hence, many of the newly developed suggestions, procedures, and guidelines for digital trace data can also be applied to combined survey and digital trace data. For the same reason, many of the new ideas that are being discussed for digital trace data will also benefit researchers and archivists working with linked survey and

¹¹ Archiving Social Media Data: Challenges and Proposed Solutions [Webinar], <https://zenodo.org/record/3875963> (date of access: 23/11/2020)

digital trace data. Two concepts that are of particular relevance here are a) the notion of data archives as trusted third parties and b) new solutions for data access. The idea that data archives can serve as trusted third parties in public-private partnerships for research with digital trace data has been put forth by several people and institutions. Data archives “have experience with and technical solutions for storing and controlling access to personal and sensitive data (typically called safe havens or secure data centres), and their goal is to maximize the use of research data while also protecting the privacy of individual participants” (Breuer et al. 2020, p. 2072). As the previous section has illustrated, many archives are very active in the development of solutions for storing digital trace data. Compared to individual researchers or universities, they may also have more leverage in negotiations with private companies, and “their capabilities in managing, documenting, and storing data can also be attractive to smaller companies that do not have a technical infrastructure for storing/archiving data” (Breuer et al., 2020, p. 2072). In addition, data archives may also be in a position to establish their own continuous (general-purpose) collections of digital trace data (besides archiving data from external researchers). Such collections could also include a combination of surveys and digital trace data, thus serving as an extension to the existing survey programmes of many archives. As digital trace data tend to be larger and often also more sensitive/disclosive than survey data, storing and providing (more of) these data also requires new solutions for data access. Some of those are described by Van Atteveldt et al. (2020). Their suggestions include the publication/sharing of small validation datasets, publishing only metadata, restricted on-site or remote access, and non-consumptive use of research data. In cases in which the publication of the full dataset is not possible (e.g., due to restrictions by ToS), making smaller validation datasets available can be one solution to allow a basic reproduction of research findings or the development or refinement of methods. If the data cannot be published or shared at all, researchers can at least publish the metadata. While metadata standards for digital trace data are still being discussed, archives have substantial expertise in the use of standardized metadata that researchers can make use of to improve the transparency and, if not direct reproducibility, at least (conceptual) replicability of their work. For very sensitive data, strict access control measures may be employed. These can entail on-site access in secure data environments or restricted remote access options. Related to the latter is the idea of remote execution (of analyses). What this means is that users are not able to directly access the data. Instead, they use a platform (e.g., an API or web interface) to send an analysis as a request to a server/database that holds the data and receive a result as an output in return. Such solutions are currently being planned, developed, and tested, e.g., as part of the SOMAR infrastructure at ICPSR and as an extension to the GESIS Notebooks service at GESIS.¹² As these examples show, the field of digital trace data in the social sciences is very dynamic, and the developments in research and at archives in the coming years will likely provide many new opportunities for researchers working with linked survey and digital trace data.

¹² GESIS Notebooks, <https://notebooks.gesis.org/> (date of access: 23/11/2020)

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